

BBMRI-ERIC Directory

Manual for data managers

Version 4.3.2

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Glossary

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project Project run by BBMRI-ERIC supported by the Horizon 2020 grant number 676550 (implementation and Operation of the gateway for health into BBMRI-ERIC – ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC). 94

API Application Programming Interface. 85, 86

BBMRI Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure. 6, 31, 85

BBMRI-ERIC Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium. 6, 7, 38, 85–87

CSV Comma-Separated Values. 7, 12, 14, 15

DICOM Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) is a standard for handling, storing, printing, and transmitting information in medical imaging. It includes a file format definition and a network communications protocol. 26

DUC Digital Use Conditions. 27

DUO Data Use Ontology. 91

EMBL-EBI European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute. 38

EMX2 Entity Model eXtension 2 backend used by MOLGENIS. 92

ERIC European Research Infrastructure Consortium. 6

ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th revision, provided by World Health Organization (WHO). See <http://www.who.int/classifications/icd/en/>. 25, 36, 38

ID Identifier. 17, 23, 85, 86

ISO-3166-1 ISO 3166-1 standard for country codes. 17, 18, 20–22, 28–34, 36, 37

ISO8601 ISO 8601 date and time format. 15

Member EU Member States, third countries as well as intergovernmental organisations may become Members BBMRI-ERIC. 5

MIABIS Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing (MIABIS), community standard for representing biobanks and their contents. See <https://github.com/MIABIS/miabis/wiki>. 25, 26, 32, 34–36

NN National Node. National Nodes means an entity, not necessarily with legal capacity, designated by a Member State, that coordinates the national Biobanks and Biomolecular Resources, and links its activities with the pan-European activities of BBMRI-ERIC. Organisational Node means an entity, not necessarily with legal capacity, designated by an intergovernmental organisation that coordinates the Biobank(s) and Biomolecular Resources of the organisation, and links its activities with those of the pan-European infrastructure, BBMRI-ERIC. 86, 91

ORPHA Orphanet identifier prefix. 25, 36, 38

PD Process Description. 27

PDF Portable Document Format. 93

PI Principal Investigator. 9, 13

QMS Quality Management System. 5

REST-API Representational State Transfer application programming interface. 91

SNOMED-CT Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms. 26, 38

SOP Standard Operating Procedure as a part of Quality Management System (QMS). 27

TRL Technology Readiness Level. See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level. Use the European Commission definition of TRL. 34

URI Uniform Resource Identifier. 38

URL Uniform Resource Locator. 18, 21, 27, 28, 31, 33, 34, 92

WGS84 World Geodetic System 1984. 19, 22, 28

WHO World Health Organization. 4

ZIP ZIP archive file format. 12, 14, 30

1. Introduction

This manual is a technical description of the BBMRI-ERIC Directory data model and the process of updating data in the Directory. The intended audience of this manual is the National Node Data Manager. Throughout this document the BBMRI-ERIC Directory is used for the examples. However, this manual also applies to local BBMRI instances. Although the model remains the same, minor differences between the local and ERIC Directories exist, these will be indicated in the footnotes.

2. Data integration process

The BBMRI-ERIC Directory has a federated process of updating the data, where each National Node is responsible for updating the data for the biobanks in the node. This is done in a staging area that gives the National Node exclusive access to update the data. Data in the Directory can be managed in four different ways as shown in the Figure 2.1 on the following page:

1. Manual data entry on the BBMRI-ERIC Directory through the web interface.
2. Manual upload of Excel or CSV files to the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.
3. Manual or automated upload of CSV files using `directory-tables-modifier.py` [↗](#) from `directory-scripts` [↗](#).
4. Manual data entry or upload, as in 1. and 2., but to a National Directory. Nightly synchronisation with the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.
5. Through CSV files hosted by a National Node without a National Directory. Imported nightly by the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.

Regardless of the method used to update the staging area the data from the staging area is integrated into the Directory through a nightly scheduled job. This means that it takes one day before changes are visible for the outside world. In the meantime, the data manager of the National Node can access and verify the data in the National Node's staging area.

Next to the data that is provided by the National Node the Directory holds quality marks that are based upon the self-assessment filled in by the biobanks. These parameters are managed by BBMRI-ERIC's quality management team and cannot be updated by the National Node. However, for a smooth process of application for the quality marks it is paramount that the biobank and the collections are registered in the Directory before the self-assessment is filled in.

In addition, the tables containing the data gain some extra attributes in the published production version. These are filled in automatically, e.g. backreferences, or externally, e.g. quality marks.

2.1. Manual data entry

The manual data entry option uses the form-based web interface to enter data into a staging area. This is most useful when updating or adding only a small amount of data. Data entry is done in the staging area for the National Node and changes will be automatically published to the production version on a nightly basis.

1. Go to <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu>

Figure 2.1.: Options for data ingest workflows into the Directory.

2. Click on "Sign in" in the top right corner of the screen.

LS Login, an authentication service of the European Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS RI), is a community platform established via the EOSC-Life project and operated by Masaryk University, Brno, CZ. Visit our homepage or contact us at support@sal.lifesciences-ri.eu.

The European Life Science Research Infrastructures has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 654248 and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement number 824087.

3. Sign in through your institution. If your institution is not listed, create an account with the Life-Science Hostel option (see manual). After creating your account, send an e-mail to support@molgenis.org to get the permission to enter data into the staging area of your National Node (PI in CC).

4. Click on “Navigator” in the menu.

5. On the next screen, click on the name of your national node's staging area. All staging areas are denoted by BBMRI-<CC>, where <CC> is your country code, e.g. BBMRI-CZ.

Welcome to MOLGENIS

search in schemas

3 databases found

label	description
BBMRI-CZ	Czech Staging Area
BBMRI-ERIC	BBMRI-ERIC Directory
DirectoryOntologies	Look up Lists

6. Click on the data table you want to edit.

Tables in 'BBMRI-CZ'

Download all tables: [zip](#) | [excel](#) | [jsonld](#) | [ttl](#)

search in tables

Data tables

Label	Description
AlsoKnownIn	Biobank, collection or network also exists in ...
Biobanks	Description of the biobank organisation, like name, location, network, contact person, collaboration opportunities and quality assessments.
CollectionFacts	Collection Facts
Collections	Description of the data and samples collected within a biobank, collections may be divided in sub-collections.
Networks	Description of the biobank and collection networks, like name, contact information and all kinds of common agreements (access policies, charters, sops).
Persons	Information of the contact persons of a biobank, collection of network, like name, address and e-mail address.

7. Edit the data using the edit, copy and delete buttons.

BBMRI-ERIC Tables Code Lists Data Integration Help Hi h.haagsma@umcg.nl Sign out

< BBMRI-CZ / Collections

Collections

Collections

filters columns download Table Search 1 - 20 of 106 Rows per page: 20 (required)

#	id	name	acronym	description	url	location	country	latitude	longitude
	bbmri-eric:ID:CZ_CELSPAC:collection:CELSPAC_BM	CELSPAC: BM (Breast Milk)	BM	CELSPAC: BM (Breast Milk) ...show more		Brno	Czech Republic		
	bbmri-eric:ID:CZ_CELSPAC:collection:CELSPAC_SC	CELSPAC: SC (School Children)	SC	CELSPAC: SC (Central) ...show more		Brno	Czech Republic		
	bbmri-eric:ID:CZ_CELSPAC:collection:CELSPAC_TNG	CELSPAC: TNG (The Next Generation)	TNG	The Next Generation ...show more		Brno	Czech Republic		

8. Click the edit button to open the edit window, where you can edit the data for a single record.

update into table: Collections (Collections)

Descriptives

Collection Descriptives

ID (required)
bbmri-eric:ID:CZ_CELSPAC:collection:CELSPAC_BM
Unique collection ID within BBMRI-ERIC based on MIABIS 2.0 standard, constructed from biobankID prefix + :collection: + local collection ID string - MIABIS-2.0-01.

Name (required)
CELSPAC: BM (Breast Milk)
Collection name according to MIABIS 2.0 - MIABIS-2.0-03.

Acronym
BM
Collection acronym according to MIABIS 2.0 - MIABIS-2.0-02.

Description (required)
CELSPAC: BM (Breast milk) is the biomonitoring study conducted according to the WHO protocol for the monitoring of POPs in human breast milk. The remaining samples are stored in our Biobank in glass tubes.
Collection description according to MIABIS 2.0 - MIABIS-2.0-08.

URL
Collection URL - MIABIS-2.0-04.

Location
Brno
The city where the collection is located.

Country (required)

< Previous Next > Close Save draft Save Collections

Chapters
Descriptives
Belongs to
Characteristics
Donor Data
Sample Data
Imaging Data
Policies

9. To save the record, click the 'Save <table name>' button at the bottom.

10. All changes are automatically published from staging to production during the night.

2.2. Manual data upload of Excel or CSV files

Manual upload is done in the staging area for the National Node and changes will be published to the production version on a nightly basis. The Excel file or CSV files have to adhere to a specific structure. CSV files can be bundled together in a ZIP file, where each file has the name of the table and Excel files can have multiple sheets, where each sheet has the name of the table. The names are as follows: Collections, Biobanks, Networks, Persons, CollectionFacts, AlsoKnownIn, Studies, Services.

Our data management team will provide you with a template upon request, or see section “Download the latest model and data” to retrieve a template yourself.

The steps to upload the files are as follows:

1. Go to <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu>

The screenshot shows the BBMRI-ERIC directory website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Background, Map of Biobanks, and Help, along with a Sign in button. Below the navigation bar is a search bar with a search icon and a Request button. Underneath the search bar are several filter dropdown menus: Diagnosis available, Countries, Collection type, Categories, Material type, Biobank services, Quality labels, and Network. There is also a checkbox for 'Available to commercial use'. Below the filters, the search results are displayed. The results show a total of 483 organisations, 1932 collections, and 1141 subcollections. Three biobank entries are visible: A Coruña Biobank (no collections yet), Acibadem University Biobank (1 collection available), and Acutelines (1 collection available). Each entry includes a 'View biobank' link and a 'More details' link. Below these are three more biobank entries: AGNES Biobank, ALLBIO INTERNATIONAL, and AMC Renal Transplant Biobank, each with a 'View biobank' link.

2. Click on “Sign in” in the top right corner of the screen.

LS Login, an authentication service of the European Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS RI), is a community platform established via the EOSC-Life project and operated by Masaryk University, Brno, CZ. Visit our homepage or contact us at support@sal.lifesciences-ri.eu.

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3. Sign in through your institution. If your institution is not listed, create an account with the Life-Science Hostel option (see manual). After creating your account, send an e-mail to support@molgenis.org to get the permission to enter data into the staging area of your National Node (PI in CC).

4. Click on “Navigator” in the menu.

5. On the next screen, click on the name of your national node's staging area. All staging areas are denoted by BBMRI-<CC>, where <CC> is your country code, e.g. BBMRI-CZ.

Tables in 'BBMRI-CZ'

Download all tables: [zip](#) | [excel](#) | [jsonld](#) | [ttl](#)

search in tables

Data tables

Label	Description
AlsoKnownIn	Biobank, collection or network also exists in ...
Biobanks	Description of the biobank organisation, like name, location, network, contact person, collaboration opportunities and quality assessments.
CollectionFacts	Collection Facts
Collections	Description of the data and samples collected within a biobank, collections may be divided in sub-collections.
Networks	Description of the biobank and collection networks, like name, contact information and all kinds of common agreements (access policies, charters, sops).
Persons	Information of the contact persons of a biobank, collection of network, like name, address and e-mail address.

6. Click on “Data integration”, “Upload/Download”.

Tables in 'BE'

Download all tables: [zip](#) | [excel](#) | [jsonld](#) | [ttl](#)

search in tables

Data tables

Label	Description
AlsoKnownIn	Biobank, collection or network also exists in ...
Biobanks	Description of the biobank organisation, like name, location, network, contact person, collaboration opportunities and quality assessments.
CollectionFacts	Collection Facts
Collections	Description of the data and samples collected within a biobank, collections may be divided in sub-collections.
Networks	Description of the biobank and collection networks, like name, contact information and all kinds of common agreements (access policies, charters, sops).
Persons	Information of the contact persons of a biobank, collection of network, like name, address and e-mail address.

7. Click 'Browse', select your Excel, CSV or ZIP file to upload and click 'Import'.

BBMRI-ERIC[®] Tables Code Lists Data Integration Help Hi h.haagsma@umcg.nl Sign out

Up/Download for BBMRI-CZ

Upload

Import and export data (tables) and metadata (schema, settings) in bulk.
Import data by uploading files in excel, csv, zip, json or yaml format.

BBMRI-CZ1730991527051.zip

Download

Export data by downloading various file formats:

Export schema as [csv](#) / [json](#) / [yaml](#)

Export all data as [excel](#) / [csv.zip](#) / [tli](#) / [jsonld](#)

Export specific tables:

- AlsoKnownIn: [csv](#) / [excel](#)
- Biobanks: [csv](#) / [excel](#)
- CollectionFacts: [csv](#) / [excel](#)
- Collections: [csv](#) / [excel](#)
- Networks: [csv](#) / [excel](#)
- Persons: [csv](#) / [excel](#)

Note to programmers: the GET endpoints above also accept http POST command for updates, and DELETE commands for deletions.

8. During the upload, progress is shown on screen. Successful uploads are shown in green, warnings in yellow, and errors in red. Warnings might occur when your file contains additional columns or when it does not provide data for optional columns. At the end, click 'Done' to complete the process. If the upload fails, please take a screenshot of the error report and contact the helpdesk.

BBMRI-ERIC[®] Tables Code Lists Data Integration Help Admin Hi admin Sign out

Up/Download for BBMRI-CZ

Progress of current upload:

- ✓ Import csv file in 3140ms
 - ✓ Import metadata in 1195ms
 - ✓ Loaded tables and columns from 'molgenis' sheet
 - ✓ Loaded 3 members from 'molgenis_members' sheet
 - ✓ Loaded settings from 'molgenis_settings' sheet
- ✓ Import from store in 1823ms
 - ✓ Skipped table AlsoKnownIn : sheet was empty in 2ms
 - ✓ Imported 20 Persons in 161ms (124 items/sec)
 - ✓ Imported 8 Networks in 61ms (131 items/sec)
 - ✓ Imported 9 Biobanks in 105ms (85 items/sec)
 - ✓ Imported 106 Collections in 554ms (191 items/sec)
 - ✓ Imported 375 CollectionFacts in 937ms (400 items/sec)
- ✓ Committing in 78ms

2.2.1. Structure of the CSV files

The CSV files should be well structured and adhere to a few specific rules:

- No embedded newlines
- Text should be enclosed with double quotes
- Lists should be enclosed with double quotes and use commas as separator for the list elements
- Dates should be ISO8601 formatted
- When there is no value for a certain field you should leave it completely empty

3. Data model

The data model of the directory consists of 8 entities that have to be managed by the National Nodes and several look-up lists for the acceptable values for the fields.

1. Persons: Describes contact information for biobanks, collections or networks
2. AlsoKnownIn: Describes the source in which the biobank, collection or networks also exists
3. Networks: Describes networks of collaborating biobanks
4. Biobanks: Describes the biobank organisation
5. Collections: Describes the biobank collections and subcollections
6. CollectionFacts: Describes aggregates of samples of the collections
7. Studies: Describes the studies in which context the collection was generated
8. Services: Describes the services that the biobank offers to researchers, for example sequencing, sample and bioanalytical services, or bioinformatics and data sciences services.

For simplicity, the supporting entities that describe the look-up lists are not described in this manual. The model can be visually represented as shown in Figure 3.1 on the next page.

3.1. Download the latest model and data

The latest model and data from your National Node staging area can be obtained using the Navigator.

1. Navigate to the Up/Download screen for your National Node.
2. Choose whether you want to download the metadata, all data, or table-specific data.

The screenshot shows the BBMRI-ERIC web interface for the 'Up/Download for BBMRI-CZ' section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the BBMRI-ERIC logo, links for 'Tables', 'Code Lists', 'Data Integration', and 'Help', a user profile 'Hi h.haagsma@umcg.nl', and a 'Sign out' button. The main heading is 'Up/Download for BBMRI-CZ'. Under the 'Upload' section, it says 'Import and export data (tables) and metadata (schema, settings) in bulk.' and 'Import data by uploading files in excel, csv, zip, json or yaml format.' Below this is a file upload input field with a 'Browse' button. The 'Download' section is titled 'Export data by downloading various file formats:'. It lists options: 'Export schema as csv / json / yaml', 'Export all data as excel / csv.zip / ttl / jsonld', and 'Export specific tables:'. Under 'Export specific tables:', there are bullet points for: 'AlsoKnownIn: csv / excel', 'Biobanks: csv / excel', 'CollectionFacts: csv / excel', 'Collections: csv / excel', 'Networks: csv / excel', and 'Persons: csv / excel'. At the bottom, a note states: 'Note to programmers: the GET endpoints above also accept http POST command for updates, and DELETE commands for deletions.'

Figure 3.1.: Entity relation diagram (ERD) of the entities in BBMRI-ERIC Directory which are editable by a data manager.

This provides you with the latest model including the currently available data from your National Node.

3.2. Structure of the identifiers

The Directory is a federated infrastructure, and to prevent collisions in identifiers we have defined a specific structure for the identifiers in the Directory.

Biobank ID: bbmri-eric:ID:<CC>_<local id>

Collection ID: <Biobank ID>:collection:<local id>

Network ID: bbmri-eric:networkID:<CC>_<local id>

Contact ID: bbmri-eric:contactID:<CC>_<local id>

Also Known In ID: bbmri-eric:akiID:<CC>_<local id>

Facts ID: bbmri-eric:factID:<CC>_<local id>

Study ID: bbmri-eric:studyID:<CC>_<local id>

Service ID: bbmri-eric:serviceID:<CC>_<local id>

Where <CC> has to be replaced by the valid ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code for the country of residence and <local id> with a local ID generated by the national node to be unique within its context. We advise to use the ID of the entity in the national directory if one is present. All local parts should be limited to roman letters and numbers (a-z, A-Z, 0-9).

3.3. Biobanks

The biobank entity (Biobanks) describes the biobank organisation.

Table 3.1:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_] starting with the prefix bbmri-eric.ID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code Checks: BG:BBOutsideCountry; C19:BBProsAttrNoColl, BBProsCollNoAttr, CapNeedsContent; CEX:NoCollections; MAC:IsoStageMismatch, MemberDupOtherArea, MemberNonMember; VID:BBCharsInvalid, BBEmptySeg, BBExtFormat, BBExtPrefix, BBPrefix
pid *	persistent identifier (read-only)	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters (automatically filled in)
name *	Name of the biobank	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters Checks: SE:BBNameMissing
acronym	Short name or acronym of the biobank if applicable	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 20 characters
description *	Description of the biobank in English	1	Text Checks: SE:BBDescMissing, BBDescPlaceholder, BBDescShort
url	URL of the website of the biobank	0..1	URL Checks: URL:BBInvalid, BBMissing
location	The city where the biobank is located	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
country *	The country in which the biobank resides	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code Checks: BG:BBOutsideCountry; CTF:EmailCountrySuffix; MAC:IsoStageMismatch, MemberDupOtherArea, MemberNonMember

Continued on the next page

Table 3.1: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
latitude	Latitude of the location of the primary site of the biobank	0..1	WGS84 coordinate Checks: BG:BBCoordsMissing, BBLatInvalid, BBLonInvalid, BBOOutsideCountry, BBRevGeoFail
longitude	Longitude of the location of the primary site of the biobank	0..1	WGS84 coordinate Checks: BG:BBCoordsMissing, BBLatInvalid, BBLonInvalid, BBOOutsideCountry, BBRevGeoFail
head	Person in charge of the biobank.	0..1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record
contact *	Contact information of the primary external contact of the biobank	1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record Checks: BBF:ContactMissing; CTA:CollectionForeignInstitutionContact, CrossBiobankInstitutionContact
juridical_person *	Name of the organisation (legal entity) of the biobank	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters Checks: BBF:JuridicalInvalid, JuridicalMissing; MAC:MemberDupOtherArea, MemberNonMember
network	List of networks in which the biobank participants	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced network information records Checks: BCO:BBNetFlag; C19:BBNetMissing
also_known	List of also known in which are linked to collection participates	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced also known information records
collections	List of collections belonging to this biobank	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced collection information records (automatically filled in)
services	List of capabilities and services that the biobank organisation can offer to a researcher	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced service information records (automatically filled in)

Continued on the next page

Table 3.1: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
quality	The biobank is marked with this/these quality standard(s) (read-only)	0..1	Comma-separated list of quality assessment marks (externally filled in)
collaboration_commercial	Indication if the biobank is able to participate in commercial collaborations	0..1	true, false Checks: AP:BBAvailNone
collaboration_non_for_profit	Indication if the biobank is able to participate in collaborations with not-for-profit organisations	0..1	true, false Checks: AP:BBAvailNone
national_node *	The biobanks originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)
withdrawn *	This biobank is withdrawn from the Directory	0..1	true, false

3.4. Collections

The collection entity (Collections) describes the data and samples collected in the biobank at the (sub)collection level. The collection can be described with subcollections to provide detailed information on the available materials, diseases or other attributes. A collection can be subdivided on any distinct criterion, but should always maintain strict partitioning (i.e. there should not be overlap between subcollections. Each sample should be represented in only one subcollection of the collection).

N.B.: In order for COVID-19 collections to be found, the collection must be a member of the COVID-19 network (see network attribute)

Table 3.2:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
<i>Descriptives</i>			
id *	The unique identifier of the record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_] starting with the ID of the biobank in which the collection resides + :collection: Checks: BG:CollOutsideCountry; C19:AbilityNeedsPros, AbilityOoMNonZero, BslFlagMissing, CovidDiagMissing, MaterialsSuspect, NeedsDisease, ProsDataMissing, ProsNeedsDisease, ProsNeedsType, ProsOoMNonZero; CC:LargeNoSubcoll; FT:AllStarDonorGap, AllStarMissing, AllStarSizeGap, CollFactsMismatch, DnaMaterials, DnaNavPresent, DonorsZero, KAnonViolation, OneStarMissing, OneStarValue, SizeAboveAllStar, SizeBelowAllStar, SizeInvalid, SizeMissing; OC:Orphan; SNM:SubcollNetMissing; VID:CollCharsInvalid, CollEmptySeg, CollExtFormat, CollExtPrefix, CollNoBBPrefix, CollPrefix
name *	Name of the collection	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters Checks: C19:AbilityNeedsPros, AbilityOoMNonZero; CC:OrphanInvalid; SE:CollNameMissing; TXT:AgeRange, CovidDiag, FFPEMaterial, StudyType
acronym	Short name or acronym of the collection if applicable	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 20 characters
description *	Description of the collection in English	1	Text Checks: SE:CollDescMissing, CollDescPlaceholder, CollDescShort; TXT:AgeRange, CovidDiag, FFPEMaterial, StudyType
url	URL of the website of the collection	0..1	URL
location	The city where the collection is located	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
country *	The country in which the collection resides	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code Checks: BG:CollOutsideCountry

Continued on the next page

Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
latitude	Latitude of the location of the primary site of the collection	0..1	WGS84 coordinate Checks: BG:CollLatInvalid, CollLonInvalid, CollOutsideCountry, CollRevGeoFail
longitude	Longitude of the location of the primary site of the collection	0..1	WGS84 coordinate Checks: BG:CollLatInvalid, CollLonInvalid, CollOutsideCountry, CollRevGeoFail
head	Person in charge of the collection.	0..1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record
contact *	Contact information of the primary external contact of the collection	1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record Checks: CTA:CollectionForeignInstitutionContact, CrossBiobankInstitutionContact; CTR:CrossBiobankReuse
national_node *	The collection originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)
withdrawn *	This collection is withdrawn from the Directory	0..1	true, false
<i>Belongs to</i>			
parent_collection	Parent collection of which the collection is a part	0..1	Unique identifier of the referenced collection information record Checks: SNM:SubcollNetMissing
sub_collection	List of subcollections of the collection	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced collection information records (automatically filled in) Checks: CP:DonorOver, DonorUnknown, FactDonorOver, FactDonorUnknown, FactSizeOver, FactSizeUnknown, SizeOver, SizeUnknown
biobank *	The biobank that hosts the collection	1	Unique identifier of the referenced biobank information record Checks: CTA:CollectionForeignInstitutionContact, CrossBiobankInstitutionContact; CTR:CrossBiobankReuse; VID:CollNoBBPrefix

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Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
biobank_label *	The label of the biobank that hosts the collection	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters (automatically filled in)
network	List of networks in which the collection participates	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced network information records Checks: BCO:AccessConflict,FactsMissing; FT:DnaMaterials,DnaNavPresent; SNM:SubcollNetMissing
also_known	List of also known in which are linked to the collection	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced also known information records
studies	List of studies during which the collection was generated	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced study information records
<i>Characteristics</i>			
type *	The type of the sample collection	1	Comma-separated list of collection types Checks: AP:DiseaseDuoMissing; C19:TypeMissing;CC:DiagMissingDisease, DiagTypeMismatch,ImageTypeMissing, OrphaNeedsRDType,RDOrphaMissing, RDOrphaSuggest,TypeMissing; TXT:StudyType
data_categories *	The categories of data that are available as part of the collection	1..n	Comma-separated list of data categories Checks: CC:DiagCatMismatch, ImageCatMissing,ImgDataMissing, ImgModMissing,MaterialsMissing, MedRecDiagGap,SampleCatMismatch
order_of_magnitude *	Number of samples in the collection expressed as orders of magnitude	1	Integer n, where 10 ⁿ is the best approximation of the number of samples in the collection (range 0 - 8) Checks: C19:AbilityOoMNonZero, ProsOoMNonZero;CC:LargeNoSubcoll, LargeOoMOnly,SizeOoMMismatch
size	Exact size of collection in number of unique sample IDs at the point in time given in the specified timestamp	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 Checks: CC:LargeOoMOnly, SizeOoMMismatch;CP:SizeOver, SizeUnknown;FT:SizeAboveAllStar, SizeBelowAllStar,SizeInvalid,SizeMissing

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Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
categories	Collection categories based on diseases	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced categories information records (automatically filled in)
timestamp	Exact timestamp at which the size of the collection as specified in size was determined	0..1	Timestamp in ISO 8601 format (yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss+nnnn), e.g. 2016-11-15T09:53:13+0100, it is acceptable to set the time component to 00:00:00 when not known.
quality	Collection quality assessment (read-only)	0..1	Comma-separated list of quality assessment marks (automatically filled in)
combined_quality	Collection and Biobank quality assessment (read-only)	0..1	Comma-separated list of quality assessment marks (automatically filled in)
<i>Donor data</i>			
number_of_donors	Exact number of donors for whom there are samples and/or data in the collection	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 Checks: CP:DonorOver, DonorUnknown
order_of_magnitude_donors	Number of donors for whom there are samples and/or data in the collection expressed as orders of magnitude	0..n	Integer n, where 10 ⁿ is the best approximation of the size of the collection (range 0 - 8)
sex	The sex of the individuals whose samples are part of the collection	0..n	Comma-separated list of sex types Checks: FT:CollFactsMismatch

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Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
diagnosis_available	Diagnosis available in the collection	0..n	ICD-10 with the prefix urn:miriam:icd: Available diagnosis can denoted by entire chapters (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:l), blocks (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:A00-A09), or individual codes. (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:A09. OR Orphanet codes with the prefix ORPHA: (e.g. ORPHA:10). Checks: C19:DiagRange;CC:DiagRange, OrphanInvalid,OrphaNeedsIcd; FT:CollFactsMismatch;TXT:CovidDiag
age_low	Age of the youngest individual in the collection at the time the sample was taken	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 and \leq age_high Checks: CC:AgeLowBelowMin, AgeRangeInverted,AgeRangePoint, AgeUnitMissing;FT:AgeRangeBroad, AgeRangeMismatch;TXT:AgeRange
age_high	Age of the oldest individual in the collection at the time the sample was taken	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 and \geq age_low, Checks: CC:AgeHighBelowMin, AgeRangeInverted,AgeRangePoint, AgeUnitMissing;FT:AgeRangeBroad, AgeRangeMismatch;TXT:AgeRange
age_unit	Unit defining age low and age high	0..1	Comma-separated list of MIABIS age_units. Checks: CC:AgeUnitAmbiguous, AgeUnitMissing;FT:AgeUnitMismatch
facts	Collection facts for this collection	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced collection fact information records Checks: BCO:FactsMissing; CP:FactDonorOver,FactDonorUnknown, FactSizeOver,FactSizeUnknown; FT:AllStarDonorGap,AllStarMissing, AllStarSizeGap,CollFactsMismatch, DnaMaterials,DnaNavPresent,DonorsZero, KAnonViolation,OneStarMissing, OneStarValue,SizeAboveAllStar, SizeBelowAllStar,SizeInvalid,SizeMissing

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Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
<i>Sample data</i>			
materials	The types of biological material present in the collection	0..n	Comma-separated list of MIABIS material types. When specified the collection type must include Sample Collection. Checks: CC:MaterialsMissing, SampleCatMismatch; FT:CollFactsMismatch,DnaMaterials, DnaNavPresent;TXT:FFPEMaterial
storage_temperatures	The temperature at which the samples are stored	0..n	Comma-separated list of storage temperatures according to the MIABIS classification
<i>Imaging data</i>			
body_part_examined	The body part that was the target of examination for the image taken	0..n	Comma-separated list of DICOM body part codes (based on SNOMED-CT codes). When specified the collection type must include Image collection.
imaging_modality	The imaging modality used for generating the image	0..n	Comma-separated list of DICOM image modality codes. When specified the collection type must include Image collection.
image_dataset_type	The datatype of the images in the collection	0..n	Comma-separated list of DICOM image dataset types. When specified the collection type must include Image collection.
<i>Policies</i>			
collaboration_commercial	Indication if the material in the collection is available for use in a commercial context	0..1	true, false Checks: AP:BBAttrDuoConflict, BBDuoMissing,CollDuoConflict, CollDuoMissing
collaboration_non_for_profit	Indication if the material in the collection is available for use in a not-for-profit context	0..1	true, false Checks: AP:BBAttrDuoConflict, BBDuoMissing,CollDuoConflict, CollDuoMissing

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Table 3.2: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
data_use	Data access policy/policies in data use ontology format.	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced data use ontology Checks: AP:BBAttrDuoConflict, BBDuoMissing, BioDuoMissing, CollDuoConflict, CollDuoMissing, DataRetDuo, DiseaseDuoMissing, DuoMissing, GenericDuoMissing, JointDuo
duc_profile	Link to the Digital Use Conditions (DUC) profile	0..1	URL
commercial_use	Indication if commercial users can request access to samples and/or data	0..1	true, false Checks: BCO:AccessConflict
access_fee	Indication if an access fee is required for access to samples, data or imaging	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of access types Checks: AP:AccessMissing
access_joint_project	Indication if a joint project is required for access to samples, data or imaging	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of access types Checks: AP:AccessMissing
access_description	Short description of the conditions for access to samples, data or imaging in English	0..1	Text Checks: AP:AccessMissing
access_uri	URL to a detailed description of the access conditions for access to samples, data or imaging	0..1	URL Checks: AP:AccessMissing; URL:CollDataInvalid, CollImageInvalid, CollSampleInvalid
sop	Indication of the availability of Process Descriptions (PDs) and/or Standard Operating Procedures (SOP's).	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of SOP's

3.5. Networks

The network entity (Networks) describes a network of biobanks.

Table 3.3:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	The unique identifier of the record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_] starting with the prefix bbmri-eric:networkID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code Checks: VID:NetCharsInvalid,NetCountry, NetEmptySeg,NetExtPrefix,NetPrefix
name *	The name of the network	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
acronym	Short name or acronym of the network, if applicable	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 20 characters
description *	Description of the network, in English	1	Text
location	The city where the network is located	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
latitude	Latitude of the location of the primary site of the network	0..1	WGS84 coordinate
longitude	Longitude of the location of the primary site of the network	0..1	WGS84 coordinate
also_known	List of also known in which are linked to collection participates	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced also known information records
url	URL of the website of the network	0..1	URL
juridical_person	Name of the organisation (legal entity) of the network	0..1	Text
contact *	Contact information of the primary external contact of the network	1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record

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Table 3.3: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
common_network_elements	elements who are the same for all biobanks/collections within the network	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of common network elements
national_node *	The network originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)
withdrawn *	This network is withdrawn from the Directory	1	true, false

3.6. Persons

The contact information entity (Persons) describes the contact information for a biobank, collection or network.

Table 3.4:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_], starting with bbmri-eric:contactID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code. Checks: VID:CtCharsInvalid,CtEmptySeg,CtExtFormat,CtExtPrefix,CtPrefix
title_before_name	Titles that are prefixed to the name	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
first_name	First name of the person to contact	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters Checks: CTF:FirstNameMissing
last_name	Last name of the person to contact	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters Checks: CTF:LastNameMissing

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Table 3.4: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
title_after_name	Titles that are appended to the name (e.g. MD, PhD)	0..1	Test, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
email *	E-mail address to contact	1	text Checks: CTA:CollectionForeignInstitutionContact, CrossBiobankInstitutionContact; CTF:EmailCountrySuffix,EmailInvalid, EmailMissing,EmailPlaceholder, EmailUnreachable
phone	Telephone number including international prefix	0..1	Compliant to the E.123 norm, international notation including the international access number and using spaces to visually separate groups of numbers, e.g. +31 20 1234567 Checks: CTF:PhoneInvalid,PhoneMissing
address	Address including routing information where necessary	0..1	text
zip	ZIP or postal code	0..1	text
city	City	0..1	text
country*	Country	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code
role	Official role of the person	0..1	text
biobanks	Person is linked to this/these biobank(s)	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the biobank information records (automatically filled in)
collections	Person is linked to this/these collection(s)	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the collection information records (automatically filled in) Checks: CTA:CrossBiobankInstitutionContact; CTR:CrossBiobankReuse

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Table 3.4: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
networks	Person is linked to this/these network(s)	0..1	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the network information records (automatically filled in)
national_node *	The contact originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)

3.7. Also known in

The “also known in” entity (AlsoKnownIn) describes where the network, biobank or collection also exists, i.e. other directories, catalogues, repositories which contain an entry for the given network, biobank or collection. For example, a biobank included in the BBMRI Directory might also be listed in the BiobankSQAN list of biobanks.

Table 3.5:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_], starting with bbmri-eric:akID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code. (automatically generated field)
name_system *	Name of the source in which the biobank, collection or network also exists	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
pid	Persistent Identifier of the biobank, collection or network in the other source	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
url *	Link to the biobank, collection or network in the other source	1	URL
national_node *	The “also known in” originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)

3.8. Studies

The “study” entity (Studies) describes the studies in which context the collection was generated.

Table 3.6:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_], starting with bbmri-eric:studyID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code. (automatically generated field)
title *	The title of the study	1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
description	A text describing the study	0..1	Text, maximum 255 characters, recommended to be less than 60 characters
type	The type of study (observational, interventional)	0..1	Text
sex	The sex of the individuals that participated to the study	0..n	Comma-separated list of sex types
age_low	Age of youngest sample donor at time of sample donation	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 and \leq age_high
age_high	Age of oldest sample donor at time of sample donation	0..1	Integer ≥ 0 and \geq age_low,
age_unit	Unit defining Age Low and Age High.	0..1	One of MIABIS age_units.
number_of_subjects	The number of subjects that participated to the study	0..1	Integer ≥ 0
also_known	The study also exists in ...	0..n	Comma-separated list of unique identifiers of the referenced also known information records

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Table 3.6: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
collections	Person is linked to this collection	0..1	(automatically filled field)
national_node *	The “study” originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)

3.9. Services

The “service” entity (Services) describes services that biobanks offer to researchers, for example sequencing, sample and bioanalytical services, or bioinformatics and data sciences services.

Table 3.7:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_], starting with bbmri-eric:serviceID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code. (automatically generated field)
name *	Name of the service (preferably in English)	1	Text
serviceTypes *	Related service types	1..n	Comma-separated list of ServiceTypes
acronym	Short name in use for the service, if applicable.	0..1	Text
description *	Full description of the service (in English)	1	Text
descriptionUrl	URL address of the service description, if available	0..1	URL
device	Name of the device(s), if the service is provided with the use of them	0..1	Text
deviceSystem	Name of a software system or platform, if important for the device characteristics	0..1	Text

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Table 3.7: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
TRL	Technology Readiness Level - a concept for self-assessment of the service maturity	0..1	One of TRLs
accessDescription *	Description of the access policy of the service	1	Text
accessDescriptionUrl	URL of the service access policy, if available	0..1	URL
unitOfAccess	Information about a standard unit used in calculations of costs of service provision	0..1	Text
unitCost	Cost per unit	0..1	Text
qualityStandards	The standards and/or technical specifications that the service is certified or accredited for	0..n	(automatically filled field)
contactInformation	Contact information for the contact person or responsible person of the service	0..1	Unique identifier of the referenced contact information record
national_node *	The "service" originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)
biobank *	Reference to the biobank to which the service belongs	1	Unique identifier of the referenced biobank

3.10. Star Model

In order to generate aggregated data from individual level data the "fact table/ star model" can be used. Which is a special form of a *Dimensional Data Model* developed.

The star schema is the simplest form or building block of a dimensional data model organising data into facts and dimensions. A fact table contains the numeric measures produced by an operational measurement event. Within the Star Model data schema, a fact is an itemised entity that is countable or measurable and is characterised by a number of attributes which are grouped into so-called dimensions (attributes in the table below). The MIABIS Star Model selects only the most important data elements from the MIABIS core components (see table below).

The fact table provides a tool for researchers to run feasibility queries and find suitable donors, samples, and/or data for their research question.

Queries like:

- the number of donors with certain characteristics

- the number of samples with certain characteristics
- the number of data sets with certain characteristics
- the number of collections with certain characteristics

or arbitrary combinations of these can be answered with the implemented data model at MIABIS core level.

Because of the adopted method of data creation and collection the number of donors presented in the table below should not be added as it may give the wrong sums.

The Directory is a publicly available discovery service and therefore the fact-sheet content is expected to remain highly aggregated, with low residual re-identification risk after aggregation/anonymization.

For this reason, the recommended donor k-anonymity baseline for publicly exposed fact rows is $k=10$. This recommendation can differ for specific justified cases, for example when a collection is already pre-anonymized in the authoritative source under a documented policy and governance process.

Operational scenarios for k-anonymity in CollectionFacts. The Directory tooling supports multiple operational paths to reach the same k-anonymity target:

- **K-anonymize at source, then import as-is.** If your primary source system already outputs k-anonymized fact rows, import directly into the node staging area (for example with `directory-tables-modifier.py -s BBMRI-XX -T CollectionFacts -i facts.tsv -N XX`).
- **Import complete source output and apply k in the importer.** If source output is complete (not pre-filtered), apply k-anonymity during import/sync in `directory-tables-modifier.py`. Donor-based filtering is recommended (`-k 10`); sample-based filtering is optional (`-K ...`) and should be justified by the local policy because it can remove additional rows.
- **Retrofit existing staging data via QC checks + updater.** Export QC-driven fixes using `data-check.py -U ...` and apply them with `qcheck-updater.py`. For k-anonymity cleanup, run the `FT:KAnonViolation` fixes in review mode first (`--list` and/or `-n`), then apply after curator approval.

Scope of anonymization metrics in CollectionFacts. More advanced privacy metrics such as l-diversity or t-closeness are intentionally not enforced in the Directory CollectionFacts workflow. CollectionFacts is intentionally low-dimensional and already highly aggregated for public discovery use; adding stricter multidimensional privacy constraints at this layer would often suppress a large fraction of rows and materially reduce findability/utility for feasibility queries. Where stricter privacy guarantees are required by local governance, they should be applied in the authoritative upstream source before data is exported to the Directory staging area.

The Star Model entity “`eu_bbmri_eric_facts`” describes the individual level data of the collection

Table 3.8:

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
id *	Unique identifier of this record (read-only)	1	[a-z][A-Z][0-9][:-_], starting with bbmri-eric:factID: + ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code. Checks: FT:AllStarDonorGap, AllStarMissing, AllStarSizeGap, CollFactsMismatch, DnaMaterials, DnaNavPresent, DonorsZero, KAnonViolation, OneStarMissing, OneStarValue, SizeAboveAllStar, SizeBelowAllStar, SizeInvalid, SizeMissing
collection *	The collection that hosts the facts	1	Unique identifier of the referenced collection
sex	The sex of the individuals whose samples are part of the collection	0..1	List of sex types Checks: FT:CollFactsMismatch
age_range	Unit defining age of sample donor at time of sample donation	0..1	List of age ranges.
sample_type	The types of biological material	0..1	list of MIABIS material types. When specified the facts type must include Sample Collection.
disease	Diagnosis available in the collection	0..1	ICD-10 with the prefix urn:miriam:icd: Available diagnoses Use only the individual codes. (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:A09. OR Orphanet codes with the prefix ORPHA: (e.g. ORPHA:10). Do not use entire chapters (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:l), blocks (e.g. urn:miriam:icd:A00-A09)
number_of_samples	Exact number of samples and/or data in the collection	0..1	Integer \geq 0
number_of_donors	Exact number of donors for whom there are samples and/or data in the collection	0..1	Integer \geq 0

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Table 3.8: (Continued)

Attribute * = Mandatory	Description	Cardinality	Acceptable values
last_update*	Date the fact information was last updated in the source system	1	YYYY-MM-DD
national_node *	The collection this “fact” originates from this national node	1	ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 country code (automatically filled in)

4. Code lists

The Directory uses code lists to specify the acceptable options where there is a limited choice. Options can be referenced by their identifier and if an attribute can contain only one value the attribute value will be directly set to this identifier. Code lists themselves are maintained by BBMRI-ERIC and cannot be updated by a National Node's data manager.

4.1. Disease types

The disease type is designed to be an extensible, ontology based code list. Currently it comprises the ICD-10 and Orphanet ontologies, but in the future other disease ontologies such as SNOMED-CT might be included. To support this extensibility the ICD-10 codes have been prefixed with the URI scheme `urn:miriam:icd:` (e.g. `urn:miriam:icd:C19`, `urn:miriam:icd:C00-C97`) as specified by the Miriam registry team EMBL-EBI. The disease types table contains entries for all levels of the ICD-10 ontology, chapters, blocks and codes and sub codes. Data integrators should refrain from creating other blocks of contiguous codes that are not specified in ICD-10. For sources that contain disease codes in another ontology data integrators should convert these to the corresponding ICD-10 codes. Both SNOMED-CT and Orphanet maintain mappings for their ontologies. It is strongly advised to provide individual codes instead of blocks of codes. For the Orphanet codes the prefix `ORPHA:` can be used (e.g. `ORPHA:10`).

5. Data quality framework

This section documents how to run the validation checks from the `directory-scripts` repository and provides the full catalog of checks below.

Setup and run (`directory-scripts`).

- Requirements: Python ≥ 3.6 and the dependencies listed in `../directory-scripts/requirements.txt` (install with `pip3 install -r ../directory-scripts/requirements.txt`).
- If you use Python 3.12+, install the patched Yapsy wheel described in `../directory-scripts/README.md`.
- Optional: place `en_product1.xml` (ORPHA) next to `data-check.py` to enable ORPHA→ICD checks.
- Run the default validation suite: `python3 ../directory-scripts/data-check.py`
- Purge caches and write an XLSX report: `python3 ../directory-scripts/data-check.py --purge-all-caches -X results.xlsx`
- Verbose run with directory cache purge only: `python3 ../directory-scripts/data-check.py -v --purge-cache directory -N -X results.xlsx`

This chapter documents the automated checks executed by `data-check.py` in the `directory-scripts` repository. The script discovers plugins in `checks/` (Yapsy metadata + Python implementation) and emits `DataCheckWarning` records with a severity level (ERROR, WARNING, INFO). Each check below is assigned a unique identifier in the format `PluginName:NN`. These identifiers are referenced from the data model tables as *Checks*: links.

Handling reviewed false positives. Reviewed false positives can be suppressed per exact check-and-entity pair using `warning-suppressions.json`. The preferred format stores explicit metadata (for example reason, reviewer, dates, expiry) together with explicit targets controlling whether the runtime warning, the attached automated fix proposal, or both should be suppressed; legacy simple mappings remain accepted for backward compatibility. By default, one structured suppression entry suppresses both the warning row and any attached exported fix proposal for the same reviewed false positive. Suppressions should be used only for residual reviewed cases; deterministic check logic should be fixed whenever possible.

When `data-check.py` runs, it validates suppression metadata and reports non-fatal diagnostics (for example unknown check IDs, stale entity IDs, and expired entries). In debug mode, suppressed warnings are listed in the runtime log for traceability.

5.1. Emit shareable AI-curated findings from `ai-check-cache`

Emit shareable AI-reviewed findings stored in `ai-check-cache` for issues that cannot be expressed robustly as deterministic checks. Version: 1.0

AI:Curated

- **Fields:** None explicitly detected
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** AI-reviewed finding stored in the shareable ai-check-cache repository.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the cached finding details and evidence, then update the structured metadata or narrative accordingly. If the finding can be expressed deterministically, replace it with a regular plugin check instead of keeping it in the AI cache.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AIFindings.py#L57>

5.2. Check that access policies are correctly filled

Check that access policies are correctly filled. Version: 1.0

AP:BBAvailNone

- **Fields:** collaboration_commercial, collaboration_non_for_profit
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank is available neither for commercial nor for non-for-profit collaboration
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L207>

AP:AccessMissing

- **Fields:** access_description, access_fee, access_joint_project, access_uri
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** No generic access mode enabled and no access policy (description nor URI) provided for collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L231>

AP:DuoMissing

- **Fields:** data_use
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** No Data Use Ontology (DUO) term provided in data_use attribute
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L236>

AP:GenericDuoMissing

- **Fields:** data_use
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** None of generic research use purposes provided ({DUO_terms_research}) in data_use attribute - suspect situation for a biobank registered in BBMRI-ERIC Directory, which is for research purposes. DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_terms_research)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L254>

AP:DataRetDuo

- **Fields:** data_use
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Data return is not required (missing {DUO_term_data_return}) in data_use attribute - it is recommended for biobanks to support it based on BBMRI-ERIC Access policy (but not required). DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term_data_return)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L284>

AP:JointDuo

- **Fields:** data_use
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Joint projects for sample/data/image access specified and {DUO_term_joint_project} is not specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term_joint_project)}

- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L301>

AP:CollDuoMissing

- **Fields:** collaboration_commercial, collaboration_non_for_profit, data_use
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** At least one of {attributes} specified on collection level but '{DUO_term}' is not specified in data_use attribute (may be however intentional). DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L317>

AP:BBDuoMissing

- **Fields:** collaboration_commercial, collaboration_non_for_profit, data_use
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** At least one of {attributes} specified on biobank level and not overridden on collection but '{DUO_term}' is not specified in data_use attribute (may be however intentional). DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L330>

AP:CollDuoConflict

- **Fields:** collaboration_commercial, collaboration_non_for_profit, data_use
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** At least one of {attributes} specified on collection level but conflicting '{DUO_term}' is specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L345>

AP:BBAttrDuoConflict

- **Fields:** collaboration_commercial, collaboration_non_for_profit, data_use
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** At least one of {attributes} specified on biobank level and not overridden on collection but conflicting '{DUO_term}' is specified in data_use attribute. DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L347>

AP:DiseaseDuoMissing

- **Fields:** data_use, type
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Collection is disease specific but '{DUO_term_disease_specific}' is not specified in data_use attribute (may be false-positive). DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term_disease_specific)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L352>

AP:BioDuoMissing

- **Fields:** data_use
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Collection contains biological material types '{materials}' but ethics approval needed '{DUO_term_ethics_needed}' is not specified in data_use attribute (may be false-positive). DUO documentation available at {DUOs_to_url(DUO_term_ethics_needed)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/AccessPolicies.py#L368>

5.3. Checks related to the BBMRI Cohorts in the Directory

Checks content related to the BBMRI Cohorts Version: 1.0

BCO:AccessConflict

- **Fields:** commercial_use, network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** A collection is flagged for BBMRI Cohorts or BBMRI Cohorts DNA, but commercial access is not allowed on the collection or on its parent biobank.
- **Fix/Debug:** If the collection should not support commercial collaboration, remove the BBMRI Cohorts / BBMRI Cohorts DNA network flag from the collection. Otherwise correct the commercial access settings, including the parent biobank field 'collaboration_commercial'.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BBMRICohorts.py#L36>

BCO:FactsMissing

- **Fields:** facts, network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection in BBMRI cohorts {BBMRICohortsList} but the fact table is missing
- **Fix/Debug:** Prepare the facts table for the collection and upload
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BBMRICohorts.py#L159>

BCO:BBNetFlag

- **Fields:** network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** A biobank itself is linked to a BBMRI Cohorts network, but these network flags must be assigned only at collection level.
- **Fix/Debug:** Remove the BBMRI Cohorts / BBMRI Cohorts DNA network flag from the biobank. Apply these network flags only to the specific collections that belong in the cohort programme.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BBMRICohorts.py#L179>

5.4. Check relevant fields of the biobank

Check relevant fields of the biobank. Version: 1.0

BBF:JuridicalMissing

- **Fields:** juridical_person
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing juridical person ('juridical_person' attribute is empty)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankFields.py#L40>

BBF:JuridicalInvalid

- **Fields:** juridical_person
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid juridical person ('juridical_person' attribute has an invalid value - offending value: ")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankFields.py#L42>

BBF:ContactMissing

- **Fields:** contact
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing valid contact for the biobank
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankFields.py#L52>

5.5. Check that geo coordinates of the biobank are within the given country.

Check that geo coordinates of the biobank are within the given country. Version: 1.0

BG:BBLatInvalid

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid biobank latitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value ”
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L138>

BG:BBLonInvalid

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid biobank longitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value ”
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L140>

BG:BBOutsideCountry

- **Fields:** address, country, country_code, id, latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Geolocation of the biobank is likely outside of its country ; biobank seems to be in based on geographical coordinates 'latitude'={biobank['latitude']} 'longitude'={biobank['longitude']}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L158>

BG:BBRevGeoFail

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Reverse geocoding of the biobank location failed ()
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L161>

BG:BBCoordsMissing

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Missing geographical coordinates ('latitude and/or 'longitude' attributes are empty)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L164>

BG:CollLatInvalid

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid collection latitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value "
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L170>

BG:CollLonInvalid

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid collection longitude (should be a decimal number with period without any spaces or stray characters around - the surrounding quotes are added in this report): offending value "

- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L172>

BG:CollOutsideCountry

- **Fields:** address, country, country_code, id, latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Geolocation of the collection is likely outside of its country ; collection seems to be in based on geographical coordinates 'latitude'={collection['latitude']} 'longitude'={collection['longitude']}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L192>

BG:CollRevGeoFail

- **Fields:** latitude, longitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Reverse geocoding of the collection location failed ()
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/BiobankGeo.py#L195>

5.6. COVID-19 related checks of the Directory

Checks COVID-19 related content of the Directory on both collection and biobank level Version: 1.0

C19:DiagRange

- **Fields:** diagnosis_available
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The collection uses diagnosis range values in 'diagnosis_available', which prevents reliable COVID-19 search and filtering.
- **Fix/Debug:** Replace diagnosis ranges with explicit diagnosis terms or codes that the Directory search can index correctly. Do not encode ranges as diagnosis values for COVID-19 collections.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L263>

C19:BBNetMissing

- **Fields:** network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** A biobank has at least one COVID-19 collection, but the biobank is not linked to the BBMRI-ERIC COVID-19 network.
- **Fix/Debug:** If the biobank really hosts a COVID-19 collection, add the COVID-19 network to the biobank. Otherwise review the collection diagnosis coding or remove the collection from the COVID-19 dataset.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L268>

C19:BBCovidCapMissing

- **Fields:** covid19
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank contains COVID collection but does not have "covid19" attribute in "capabilities" section of attributes
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L270>

C19:TypeMissing

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The collection has no type assigned, so COVID-19-specific validation cannot determine how it should be classified.
- **Fix/Debug:** Set at least one collection type. For COVID-19 collections, make sure the type assignment matches the actual collection role, such as DISEASE_SPECIFIC and, when applicable, PROSPECTIVE_COLLECTION.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L274>

C19:ProsNeedsDisease

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Prospective COVID-19 collections must have DISEASE_SPECIFIC as one of its types

- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L279>

C19:ProsNeedsType

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Prospective COVID-19 collections must have PROSPECTIVE_COLLECTION as one of its types
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L292>

C19:ProsOoMNonZero

- **Fields:** id, order_of_magnitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Prospective collection type represents capability of setting up prospective collections - hence it should have zero order of magnitude
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L305>

C19:ProsDataMissing

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** COVID19PROSPECTIVE collection misses COVID-19 diagnosis or COVID-19 controls filled in
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L307>

C19:AbilityNeedsPros

- **Fields:** id, name
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection having "ability to collect" does not have COVID19PROSPECTIVE label
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L311>

C19:AbilityOoMNonZero

- **Fields:** id, name, order_of_magnitude
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Prospective collection type represents capability of setting up prospective collections - hence it should have zero order of magnitude
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L314>

C19:NeedsDisease

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Existing COVID-19 collections must have DISEASE_SPECIFIC as one of its types
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L324>

C19:MaterialsSuspect

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Suspect material types: existing COVID-19 collection does not have any of the common material types: DNA, PATHOGEN, PERIPHERAL_BLOOD_CELLS, PLASMA, RNA, SALIVA, SERUM, WHOLE_BLOOD, FECES, BUFFY_COAT, NASAL_SWAB, THROAT_SWAB
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L337>

C19:BslFlagMissing

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Suspect situation: collection contains infectious material (nasal/throat swabs, faeces) while the parent biobank does not indicate BSL2 nor BSL3 available
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L339>

C19:CovidDiagMissing

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** COVID19 collection misses COVID-19 diagnosis filled in
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L341>

C19:BBNetNeedsAttr

- **Fields:** covid19
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank is part of but does not have covid19 among covid19biobank attributes
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L381>

C19:BBAttrNeedsNet

- **Fields:** covid19
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank has covid19 among covid19biobank attributes but is not part of
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L383>

C19:CapNeedsContent

- **Fields:** covid19, id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank has covid19 among capabilities but has no relevant services nor any collection of COVID-19 samples nor any collection of COVID-19 controls
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L392>

C19:BBProsAttrNoColl

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Biobank has ProspectiveCollections among covid19biobank attributes but has no prospective collection defined (collection ID matching " regex pattern)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L395>

C19:BBProsCollNoAttr

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank has prospective COVID-19 collection defined but ProspectiveCollections is not among covid19biobank attributes
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:**
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/COVID.py#L398>

5.7. Check URLs

Check URLs. Version: 1.0

URL:BBMissing

- **Fields:** url
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing URL
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CheckURLs.py#L127>

URL:BBInvalid

- **Fields:** url
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank URL
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CheckURLs.py#L130>

URL:CollDataInvalid

- **Fields:** data_access_uri
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Data access URL for collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CheckURLs.py#L139>

URL:CollSampleInvalid

- **Fields:** sample_access_uri
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Sample access URL for collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CheckURLs.py#L145>

URL:CollImageInvalid

- **Fields:** image_access_uri
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Image access URL for collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CheckURLs.py#L150>

5.8. Checks content advertised by the collections.

Checks content advertised by the collections. Version: 1.0

CC:OrphaInvalid

- **Fields:** diagnosis_available, name
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Invalid ORPHA code found: %s
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L289>

CC:DiagRange

- **Fields:** diagnosis_available
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** It seems that diagnoses contains range - this will render the diagnosis search ineffective for the given collection. Violating diagnosis term(s):
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L291>

CC:TypeMissing

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection type not provided
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L295>

CC:SizeOoMMismatch

- **Fields:** order_of_magnitude, size
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Size of the collection does not match its order of magnitude: size = , order of magnitude is %d (size between %d and %d)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L299>

CC:LargeNoSubcoll

- **Fields:** id, order_of_magnitude
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Suspicious situation: large collection (> 100,000 samples or cases) without subcollections; unless it is a really homogeneous collection, it is advisable to refine such a collection into sub-collections to give users better insight into what is stored there
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L304>

CC:LargeOoMOnly

- **Fields:** order_of_magnitude, size
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Suspicious situation: large collection (> 1,000,000 samples or cases) without exact size specified
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L308>

CC:DiagMissingDisease

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** No diagnoses provide for HOSPITAL or DISEASE_SPECIFIC or RD collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L312>

CC:DiagTypeMismatch

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Diagnoses provided but none of HOSPITAL, DISEASE_SPECIFIC, RD is specified as collection type (this may be easily false positive check)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L315>

CC:MaterialsMissing

- **Fields:** data_categories, materials
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** No material types are provided while biological samples are collected
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L318>

CC:SampleCatMismatch

- **Fields:** data_categories, materials
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Sample types advertised but BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLES missing among its data categories
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L321>

CC:MedRecDiagGap

- **Fields:** data_categories
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** No diagnoses provide for a collection with MEDICAL_RECORDS among its data categories
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L324>

CC:DiagCatMismatch

- **Fields:** data_categories
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Diagnoses provided but no MEDICAL_RECORDS among its data categories
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L327>

CC:RDOrphaMissing

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Rare disease (RD) collection without ORPHA code diagnoses
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L330>

CC:RDOrphaSuggest

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Consider adding following ORPHA code(s) to the RD collection - based on mapping ICD-10 code %s to ORPHA codes: %s
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L336>

CC:OrphaNeedsRDType

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** ORPHA code diagnoses provided, but collection not marked as rare disease (RD) collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L340>

CC:OrphaNeedsIcd

- **Fields:** diagnosis_available
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The collection uses ORPHA diagnosis codes but does not provide matching ICD-10 diagnosis values.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add the relevant ICD-10 diagnosis codes alongside the existing ORPHA codes so the collection can also be found by users searching via ICD-10.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L354>

CC:OrphalcdSuggest

- **Fields:** code
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** ORPHA code %s provided, but its translation to ICD-10 as %s is not provided (mapping is of %s type). It is recommended to provide this translation explicitly until Directory implements full semantic mapping search.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L361>

CC:ImgModMissing

- **Fields:** data_categories
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** No image modalities provided for image collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L377>

CC:ImgDataMissing

- **Fields:** data_categories
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** No image dataset types provided for image collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L380>

CC:ImageCatMissing

- **Fields:** data_categories
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Imaging modalities or image data set found, but IMAGING_DATA is not among data categories: image_modality = %s, image_dataset_type = %s
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L383>

CC:ImageTypeMissing

- **Fields:** type
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Imaging modalities or image data set found, but collection type does not include IMAGE.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L385>

CC:AgeUnitAmbiguous

- **Fields:** age_unit
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Ambiguous specification of age_unit - only one value is permitted. Provided values %s
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L403>

CC:AgeUnitMissing

- **Fields:** age_high, age_low, age_unit
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing age_unit for provided age range:
{collection.get('age_low')}-{collection.get('age_high')}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L407>

CC:AgeHighBelowMin

- **Fields:** age_high
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Age_high is below the minimum value limit (%d %s): offending value %d
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L418>

CC:AgeLowBelowMin

- **Fields:** age_low
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Age_low is below the minimum value limit (%d %s): offending value %d
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L420>

CC:AgeRangeInverted

- **Fields:** age_high, age_low
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Age_low (%d) is higher than age_high (%d)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L424>

CC:AgeRangePoint

- **Fields:** age_high, age_low
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** Suspect situation: age_low == age_high == (%d) (may be false positive)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionContent.py#L426>

5.9. Check that at least one collection per biobank exists

Check that at least one collection per biobank exists Version: 1.0

CEX:NoCollections

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing at least one collection for biobank
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionExistence.py#L24>

5.10. Check that direct subcollections do not exceed parent totals

Check that direct subcollections never exceed their parent collection in exact counts or all-star fact-sheet totals. Version: 1.0

CP:SizeOver

- **Fields:** Collection.size, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The sum of direct subcollection sizes exceeds the parent collection size.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the parent collection size and the exact child sizes. Subcollections may cover only part of the parent, but their total must never exceed the parent total.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L92>

CP:DonorOver

- **Fields:** Collection.number_of_donors, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The sum of direct subcollection donor counts exceeds the parent collection number_of_donors.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the parent donor count and the exact child donor counts. Subcollections may be incomplete, but their donor total must never exceed the parent total.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L94>

CP:SizeUnknown

- **Fields:** Collection.size, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The parent collection size cannot be fully checked because one or more direct subcollections have no exact size.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add missing exact child sizes or confirm that the partitioning can only be checked at the order-of-magnitude level.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L96>

CP:DonorUnknown

- **Fields:** Collection.number_of_donors, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The parent collection donor count cannot be fully checked because one or more direct subcollections have no exact number_of_donors.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add missing exact child donor counts or confirm that the donor partitioning cannot be checked exactly.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L98>

CP:FactSizeOver

- **Fields:** Collection.facts, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The sum of direct subcollection all-star fact-sheet sample totals exceeds the parent all-star fact-sheet sample total.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the all-star fact rows on the parent and its direct subcollections. Child fact-sheet totals must never exceed the parent total.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L100>

CP:FactDonorOver

- **Fields:** Collection.facts, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The sum of direct subcollection all-star fact-sheet donor totals exceeds the parent all-star fact-sheet donor total.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the all-star donor totals on the parent and its direct subcollections. Child fact-sheet totals must never exceed the parent total.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L102>

CP:FactSizeUnknown

- **Fields:** Collection.facts, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The parent fact-sheet sample total cannot be fully checked because one or more direct subcollections have no valid all-star sample total.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add or fix the missing all-star fact rows on the affected child collections.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L104>

CP:FactDonorUnknown

- **Fields:** Collection.facts, Collection.sub_collection
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The parent fact-sheet donor total cannot be fully checked because one or more direct subcollections have no valid all-star donor total.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add or fix the missing all-star fact rows on the affected child collections.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/CollectionPartitioning.py#L106>

5.11. Check suspicious cross-biobank contact assignments

Warn when collection contacts look tied to another biobank or institution Version: 1.0

CTA:CrossBiobankInstitutionContact

- **Fields:** Contact.email, Contact.collections, Collection.contact, Collection.biobank, Biobank.contact
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** A contact is reused across biobanks even though its institutional email domain or its biobank-level role points to one specific biobank.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify whether the cross-biobank reuse is intentional. If the contact belongs to one specific biobank or institution, replace the foreign biobank collection assignments with the correct local contact.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactAssignments.py#L108>

CTA:CollectionForeignInstitutionContact

- **Fields:** Collection.contact, Collection.biobank, Contact.email, Biobank.contact
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** A collection uses a contact whose institutional email domain or biobank-level assignment points to another biobank.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review whether the collection contact was assigned by mistake. If the collection is locally managed, replace it with the correct contact for the owning biobank or document the intentional cross-biobank collaboration.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactAssignments.py#L186>

5.12. Check that contact fields are meaningful

Check that contact fields are meaningful Version: 1.0

CTF:FirstNameMissing

- **Fields:** first_name
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing first name for contact ('first_name' attribute is empty)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L254>

CTF:LastNameMissing

- **Fields:** last_name
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing last name for contact ('last_name' attribute is empty)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L256>

CTF:EmailMissing

- **Fields:** email
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing email for contact ('email' attribute is empty)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L258>

CTF:EmailInvalid

- **Fields:** email
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Email for contact is invalid - offending 'email' attribute value:
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L260>

CTF:EmailPlaceholder

- **Fields:** email
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The contact email uses a placeholder domain such as example.org, test.com, or unknown.<suffix> and is not a real operational email address.
- **Fix/Debug:** Replace the placeholder email address with a real working contact email address for the person or organisation.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L265>

CTF:EmailCountrySuffix

- **Fields:** Contact.email, Biobank.country
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The contact email uses a country-code domain suffix that does not match the linked biobank country. Generic domains and non-country staging areas such as EU and EXT are excluded.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify that the email belongs to the correct institution. If the email domain uses a country-code suffix that does not match the linked biobank country, replace it with the correct institutional email or confirm that the cross-border assignment is intentional.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L271>

CTF:EmailUnreachable

- **Fields:** email
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Email for contact seems to be unreachable because of missing DNS MX record
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L290>

CTF:PhoneMissing

- **Fields:** phone
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing phone for contact ('phone' attribute is empty')
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L302>

CTF:PhoneInvalid

- **Fields:** phone
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Phone number for contact does not conform to the E.123 international standard (means starts with + sign, no spaces) - offending phone number in 'phone' attribute:
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactFields.py#L304>

5.13. Inform when contacts are reused across biobanks

Information-level check for contacts reused by collections in multiple biobanks Version: 1.0

CTR:CrossBiobankReuse

- **Fields:** Contact.collections, Collection.contact, Collection.biobank
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** A contact is reused by collections belonging to more than one biobank.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review whether the same contact is intentionally shared across the listed biobanks. If so, this informational check can be disabled or the specific contact can be suppressed.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ContactReuse.py#L75>

5.14. Checks related to the fact tables in the Directory

Checks content related to the fact tables in the Directory Version: 1.0

FT:CollFactsMismatch

- **Fields:** diagnosis_available, facts, id, materials, sex
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** The fact sheet and the main collection record describe different diagnoses, sex groups, or material types.
- **Fix/Debug:** Align the collection-level descriptors with the fact sheet. Check diagnoses, sex, and material type values on the collection record against the values present in the fact table and correct whichever side is wrong.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L34>

FT:AgeUnitMismatch

- **Fields:** age_unit
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Age unit ID of the collection is {collection['age_unit']} while the age unit in the fact table is {factsAgeUnits}
- **Fix/Debug:** Check age unit information of the collection description with age units from the facts table and correct as necessary
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L67>

FT:AgeRangeMismatch

- **Fields:** age_high, age_low
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Fact table age outside collection age_high age_low range
- **Fix/Debug:** Check age range of the collection description with ages from the facts table and correct as necessary
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L82>

FT:AgeRangeBroad

- **Fields:** age_high, age_low
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection ages outside facts age range
- **Fix/Debug:** Check age information of the collection description with age ranges from the facts table and correct as necessary
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L84>

FT:DonorsZero

- **Fields:** all_star_number_of_donors, donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** fact table information has 0 donors/patients
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L323>

FT:KAnonViolation

- **Fields:** all_star_number_of_donors, donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** the `{len(kAnonymityViolatingList)}` records of fact table violates `{kAnonymityLimit}-anonymity: {kAnonymityViolatingList}`
- **Fix/Debug:** For public Directory data, apply a donor k-anonymity baseline of `k=10` and remove fact rows below that threshold. If the collection is already pre-anonymized under a documented policy, this rule may be reviewed as an explicit exception.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L331>

FT:AllStarMissing

- **Fields:** all_star_rows, donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Expected exactly one all-star aggregate row, found {fact_sheet['all_star_rows']}.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L347>

FT:OneStarMissing

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** missing all-but-one-star aggregate: {aggregates[3]}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L349>

FT:OneStarValue

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** INFO
- **What it checks:** missing all-but-one-star aggregate for {fk} value {value}: {aggregates[3]}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L357>

FT:AllStarSizeGap

- **Fields:** code, donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Check FT:AllStarSizeGap
- **Fix/Debug:** Check the all-star aggregate row and collection size.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L361>

FT:AllStarDonorGap

- **Fields:** code, donors_present, facts, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Check FT:AllStarDonorGap
- **Fix/Debug:** Check the all-star aggregate row and collection number_of_donors.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L363>

FT:SizeInvalid

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id, size
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection size attribute (number of samples) is not an integer
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L367>

FT:SizeAboveAllStar

- **Fields:** all_star_number_of_samples, donors_present, facts, id, size
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Value of the collection size attribute (number of samples - {collection['size']}) is greater than the all-star aggregate number_of_samples ({all_star_samples})
- **Fix/Debug:** Check size information of the collection description with the all-star row from the facts table and correct as necessary
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L369>

FT:SizeBelowAllStar

- **Fields:** all_star_number_of_samples, donors_present, facts, id, size
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Value of the collection size attribute (number of samples - {collection['size']}) is smaller than the all-star aggregate number_of_samples ({all_star_samples})
- **Fix/Debug:** Check size information of the collection description with the all-star row from the facts table and correct as necessary
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L371>

FT:SizeMissing

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id, size
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection size attribute (number of samples) not provided
- **Fix/Debug:** Add size attribute to the collection
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L373>

FT:DnaMaterials

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id, materials, network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection in {BBMRICohortsDNANetworkName} but the fact table does not contain any of the expected material types: {','.join(requiredMaterialTypes)}
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L378>

FT:DnaNavPresent

- **Fields:** donors_present, facts, id, materials, network
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Collection in {BBMRICohortsDNANetworkName} but the fact table does specified the NAV (not-available) material type
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/FactTables.py#L381>

5.15. Check that member-country institutions are not duplicated into non-member areas

Check that institutions from BBMRI member countries are kept in the correct staging area and not duplicated across member and non-member areas. Version: 1.0

MAC:IsoStageMismatch

- **Fields:** country, id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Biobank ID uses a different ISO-like country staging prefix than the biobank country.
- **Fix/Debug:** Use the member-country staging area that matches the biobank country, or correct the country attribute if the biobank is assigned to the wrong node.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/MemberAreaConsistency.py#L120>

MAC:MemberDupOtherArea

- **Fields:** country, id, juridical_person
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The same institution appears both in the member-country staging area and in another area such as EXT or EU.
- **Fix/Debug:** Keep the institution in one staging area only, or make the juridical person values distinct if the records intentionally represent different legal entities.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/MemberAreaConsistency.py#L175>

MAC:MemberNonMember

- **Fields:** country, id, juridical_person
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Institution from a BBMRI member country exists only in a non-member staging area.
- **Fix/Debug:** Move the institution to the member-country staging area if it belongs to the node. Otherwise confirm that the non-member placement is intentional and justified.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/MemberAreaConsistency.py#L193>

MAC:MemberDupOtherArea

- **Fields:** country, id, juridical_person
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** The same institution appears both in the member-country staging area and in another area such as EXT or EU.
- **Fix/Debug:** Keep the institution in one staging area only, or make the juridical person values distinct if the records intentionally represent different legal entities.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/MemberAreaConsistency.py#L213>

5.16. Check that reports orphaned collections

Check that reports orphaned collections Version: 1.0

OC:Orphan

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Orphaned collection
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/OrphanedCollections.py#L23>

5.17. Check relevant fields that they don't contain suspicious content, such as spaces only or N/A.

Check relevant fields that they don't contain suspicious content, such as spaces only or N/A. Version: 1.0

SE:BBDescMissing

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing description for biobank ('description' attribute is empty for the biobank)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L106>

SE:BBDescPlaceholder

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Biobank description uses a placeholder value instead of a real description.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L108>

SE:BBDescShort

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Suspiciously short description for biobank ('description' attribute {biobank['description']} has less than {str(minDescWords)} words)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L110>

SE:BBNameMissing

- **Fields:** name
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing name for biobank ('name' attribute is empty for the biobank)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L112>

SE:CollDescMissing

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Missing description for collection ('description' attribute is empty for the collection)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L116>

SE:CollDescPlaceholder

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection description uses a placeholder value instead of a real description.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L118>

SE:CollDescShort

- **Fields:** description
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Suspiciously short description for collection ('description' attribute {collection['description']} has less than {str(minDescWords)} words)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L120>

SE:CollNameMissing

- **Fields:** name
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** Missing name for collection ('name' attribute is empty for the biobank)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SemiemptyFields.py#L122>

5.18. Check that subcollections belong to the same network as their parent collections

Check that subcollections belong to the same network as their parent collections Version: 1.0

SNM:SubcollNetMissing

- **Fields:** id, network, parent_collection
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Subcollection is not part of network {network['id']}, even though parent collection {parent_id} is.
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/SubcollectionNetworkMembership.py#L49>

5.19. Deterministic text consistency checks

Deterministic regex/heuristic checks that compare collection narrative text with structured metadata.
Version: 0.1

TXT:AgeRange

- **Fields:** Collection.age_high, Collection.age_low, Collection.description, Collection.name
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection text suggests an age group that does not match the structured age range.
- **Fix/Debug:** Align the age_low/age_high metadata with the narrative description, or reword the narrative if the collection is broader than the text suggests.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/TextConsistency.py#L58>

TXT:StudyType

- **Fields:** Collection.description, Collection.name, Collection.type
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection text suggests a study-design concept that is missing from the structured collection type.
- **Fix/Debug:** Review the collection name/description and add the relevant structured type such as PROSPECTIVE_COLLECTION, LONGITUDINAL, or CASE_CONTROL when appropriate.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/TextConsistency.py#L71>

TXT:FFPEMaterial

- **Fields:** Collection.description, Collection.materials, Collection.name
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection text mentions FFPE/paraffin material but the structured materials do not include TISSUE_PARAFFIN_EMBEDDED.
- **Fix/Debug:** Add the structured material if paraffin-embedded tissue is really stored, or clarify in the text when the mention only refers to slides, sections, images, or derived DNA/RNA from FFPE material.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/TextConsistency.py#L84>

TXT:CovidDiag

- **Fields:** Collection.description, Collection.diagnosis_available, Collection.name
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** Collection text suggests COVID-19 disease or post-/long-COVID focus, but the structured diagnosis metadata does not reflect that context.

- **Fix/Debug:** Add the relevant structured diagnoses if the collection really targets COVID-19 or post-/long-COVID content (for example U07.* or U09.9), or reword the narrative to avoid misleading search results.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/TextConsistency.py#L97>

5.20. ID validator

ID validator Version: 1.0

VID:BBExtPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall use a permitted non-country staging prefix such as "EXT", "EU", or "IARC")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L198>

VID:BBExtFormat

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for external biobanks)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L201>

VID:BBPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** BiobankID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:_" prefix)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L204>

VID:BBCharsInvalid

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** BiobankID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L206>

VID:BBEmptySeg

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** BiobankID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L208>

VID:CollExtPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall use a permitted non-country staging prefix such as "EXT", "EU", or "IARC")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L214>

VID:CollExtFormat

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:EXT_" prefix for collections from external biobanks)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L217>

VID:CollPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** CollectionID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:ID:_" prefix)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L220>

VID:CollCharsInvalid

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** CollectionID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9;_-")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L222>

VID:CollNoBBPrefix

- **Fields:** biobank, id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** CollectionID does not contain expected biobank prefix (should start with :collection:)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L225>

VID:CollEmptySeg

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** CollectionID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L227>

VID:CtExtPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall use a permitted non-country staging prefix such as "EXT", "EU", or "IARC")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L233>

VID:CtExtFormat

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:contactID:EXT_" prefix for contacts for external biobanks)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L236>

VID:CtPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** ContactID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:contactID:_" prefix)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L239>

VID:CtCharsInvalid

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** ContactID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9:_-")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L241>

VID:CtEmptySeg

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** ContactID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L243>

VID:NetExtPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** NetworkID is not compliant with the specification (shall use a permitted non-country staging prefix such as "EXT", "EU", or "IARC")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L249>

VID:NetPrefix

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** NetworkID is not compliant with the specification (shall start with "bbmri-eric:networkID: prefix)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L251>

VID:NetCountry

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** WARNING
- **What it checks:** NetworkID has suspicious country affiliation (should start with "bbmri-eric:networkID:_" or "bbmri-eric:networkID:EU_" prefix)
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L254>

VID:NetCharsInvalid

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** NetworkID contains illegal characters (shall be "A-Za-z0-9;_")
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L256>

VID:NetEmptySeg

- **Fields:** id
- **Severity:** ERROR
- **What it checks:** NetworkID contains :: indicating empty component in ID hierarchy
- **Fix/Debug:** Verify the listed fields in the Directory UI or CSV upload and correct missing or inconsistent values.
- **Implementation:** <https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/directory-scripts/tree/master/checks/ValidateIDs.py#L258>

5.21. Metadata update helpers

The `directory-scripts` repository also contains helper tools that can propose metadata updates based on already available Directory content and on the output of the quality checks. These helpers are meant to reduce repetitive manual editing, but they are intentionally conservative and still require curator review.

Important limitation. These update workflows should only be used when the relevant BBMRI Node edits the staging area directly in Molgenis. If the staging area is synchronized or imported from another authoritative system, the correction must be made in that primary source instead. Otherwise the staging-area edit will be overwritten during the next synchronization/import.

Fact-sheet-based collection descriptor updater. `collection-factsheet-descriptor-updater.py` reads fact sheets from the public ERIC schema and proposes updates to the Collections table in an explicitly selected node staging area. The tool is intended for collection-level descriptors that can be derived conservatively from the fact sheet, for example diagnoses, material types, biological sex, age range, and total numbers of donors/samples when the all-star aggregate row is present.

- By default it only appends missing multi-value descriptors. Existing multi-value metadata is only removed or replaced when `--replace-existing` is used.
- Dry-run mode shows the proposed changes without writing them.
- Interactive mode lets the curator review the proposal before the update is applied.

- Force mode skips the interactive confirmation and applies the selected update directly.
- Fact-sheet aggregate rows (*) are treated as aggregates only, while NAV material rows are treated conservatively because k-anonymity can hide richer material-specific rows.

QC-driven updater. `data-check.py` can export a structured update plan from selected high-confidence warnings by using `-U/--export-update-plan`. The resulting JSON file can then be inspected and applied with `qcheck-updater.py`.

- `qcheck-updater.py --list` prints the proposed updates in a human-readable form.
- Dry-run mode follows the same interactive review path as a real apply, but stops before writing the changes.
- Interactive mode lets the curator review each proposed update.
- Force mode applies all selected non-conflicting updates in batch.
- The updater can apply both collection-metadata updates (table `Collections`) and collection-scoped fact-row deletion updates (table `CollectionFacts`), for example for `FT:KAnonViolation` where rows violating donor k-anonymity are removed.
- The current `FT:KAnonViolation` baseline uses donor `k=10` for publicly exposed aggregated Directory data; exceptions should be documented explicitly or at least internally justified (for example pre-anonymized source data).
- The exported update plan contains advisory checksums for each update and for the file as a whole. If the file is edited afterwards, the updater warns about the checksum mismatch but still allows an explicit override.
- Each update also records the expected live value seen when the plan was exported. If the live staging-area value changed before the update is applied, the updater warns so the curator can decide whether to continue.

The current QC-driven update modules cover access restrictions (including DUO-based access metadata), collection types, diagnoses, biological sex, material types, age ranges, and fact-sheet-derived totals where the underlying quality checks are considered certain or almost certain. Ontology-backed updates include a human-readable explanation of the term so that the curator can understand what is being applied.

6. Quality

To secure the data quality, checks are performed within the system. During the upload error messages will help correct your data input if for example IDs are not correct. Frequently BBMRI will also give warnings about the completeness of the data entry. This will be done by a python script and sended afterwards to the National nodes. Next to the quality of the data input BBMRI provides also information about the quality of biobanks, collections. BBMRI head office can assign certificates to give an indication about qualities and standards.

6.1. Quality checks data input

The table below shows the checks

Table 6.1:

Tables	Attributes	Description of the check	Check time/phase
	Error message		
persons	id	check if the ID is correct like the structure of Identity	When entering data in the database (either manually, through a file or via API) and in the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Directory
networks	id	check if the ID is correct like the structure of Identity	When entering data in the database (either manually, through a file or via API) and in the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Director
	change ID		

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Table 6.1: (Continued)

biobank	id	check if the ID is correct like the structure of Identity	When entering data in the database (either manually, through a file or via API) and in the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Director
	change ID		
collections	id	check if the ID is correct like the structure of Identity	In the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Director
	change ID		
collections	age_unit	If there is only 1 age unit selected	In the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Director
	mail to NN, contact biobank about more than one age_unit, data can not published		
collections	age high / age low	if the age high is higher that the age low	In the process of combining the data from National Nodes into the BBMRI-ERIC Director
	mail to NN, contact biobank about more than one age_unit, data can not published		

6.2. Warnings data input

The quality checks /warnings available through python scripts pay attention to attributes at different levels (biobank, collection, etc) taking care of different aspects (access policies, geolocation, etc) and raising the warnings (in *italics*) when the data provided are not compliant with the data model. Please find here the complete list of warning messages.

7. Quality marks

The results of the BBMRI-ERIC Self Assessment Survey, third-party certifications and Audits, shown as Q-marks in the Directory are managed by the BBMRI.QM team. You will not be able to update these values yourself. request a quality mark via <https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/services/self-assessment-survey/> The document below shows the workflow.

Follow the workflow below to add quality marks.

Process Flow: Q-Assessment Scheme for Biobanks and Sample Collections

Legend:

R – Requester	C – Conduct
DG – Director General	D – Decide
NND – National Node Director	P – Participate
NNQ – National Node Quality Officer	Q-mark – Quality mark
HQM – Head of Quality Management	SAS – Self-Assessment Survey
QSO – Quality Management Service Officer	REDCap™ – online software for creation of Self-Assessment Survey
	TBC – To be clarified

* ISO 20387:2018 Biotechnology – Biobanking: General requirements for biobanking;
ISO 9001: 2015 Quality managements systems – Requirements;

- ** Specifications for pre-examinations processes for:
- frozen tissue (FT) Part 1: Isolated RNA (ISO 20184-1:2018)
 - frozen tissue (FT) Part 2: Isolated proteins (ISO 20184-2:2018)
 - FFPE tissue Part 1: Isolated RNA (ISO 20166-1:2018)
 - FFPE tissue Part 2: Isolated proteins (ISO 20166-2:2018)
 - FFPE tissue Part 3: Isolated DNA (ISO 20166-3:2018)
 - venous whole blood Part 1: Isolated cellular RNA (ISO 20186-1:2019)
 - venous whole blood Part 2: Isolated genomic DNA (ISO 20186-2:2019)
 - venous whole blood Part 3: Isolated circulating cell free DNA from plasma (ISO 20186-3:2019)
 - metabolomics in urine, venous blood serum and plasma (CEN 16945:2016)
 - will be continuously updated

Description process flow symbols:

Process Flow Symbols	Meaning
	Start / End
	Activity
	Decision
	Connection to another process
	Document
	Verbal information / information via telephone, e-mail
	Connector

A. Document revisions

Table A.1:

Revision history
<p>Version: 3.5.6 Date: 20/04/2020 Author: Marije van der Geest Edits: Added COVID-19 items (<i>covid19biobank</i> and <i>COVID-19</i>) for biobank and collections table. Added code lists for <i>Services provided by the biobank</i> and <i>Relevant data and products</i>.</p>
<p>Version: 3.5.6 Date: 29/04/2020 Author: Marije van der Geest Edits: Updated lists <i>Sex</i>, <i>Material types</i>, <i>Lab standards</i> & <i>Operational standards</i>.</p>
<p>Version: 3.6 Date: 02/07/2020 Author: Marije van der Geest Edits: Added section: <i>Download latest model and data</i>.</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.1 Date: 07/07/2020 Author: Marije van der Geest Edits: Added information for national nodes and local directory instances.</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.2 Date: 28/07/2020 Author: Marije van der Geest Edits: Added Orphanet codes description for <i>diagnosis_available</i>, COVID-19 collection information and information about NN endpoints for using the REST-API</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.3 Date: 02/12/2020 Author: Brenda Hijmans Edits: Added DUO code description, changed order of some attributes in collections to match order in Molgenis</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.4 Date: 26/4/2021 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: Delete "contact priority" in biobanks, collections and networks, Deleted standard in collections and biobanks. Added quality workflow and changed the list of lab/operational standards.</p>

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Table A.1: (Continued)

<p>Version: 3.6.5 Date: 11/5/2021 Author: Esther van Enckevort Edits: Updated documentation for the order_of_magnitude and order_of_magnitude_donor fields to specify the acceptable range.</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.6 Date: 7/7/2022 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: New application pictures and reference to the codelist tabel via de menu</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.7 Date: 14/2/2023 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: qualities and warning messages, codelists via menu, proposal 1 and proposal 2</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.8 Date: 22/5/2023 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: Add starmodel & network improvements</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.9 Date: 18/10/2023 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: Cardinality</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.10 Date: 1/11/2023 Author: Aneas Hodselmans Edits: Cardinality</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.11 Date: 22/01/2024 Author: Aneas Hodselmans and Dieuwke Roelofs-Prins Edits: Withdrawn adjustments and update of some pictures</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.12 Date: 29/03/2024 Author: Aneas Hodselmans and Dieuwke Roelofs-Prins Edits: Pagenumbers</p>
<p>Version: 3.6.13 Date: 23/07/2024 Author: Aneas Hodselmans and Dieuwke Roelofs-Prins Edits: URLs and email addresses</p>
<p>Version: 4.0.0 Date: 14/10/2024 Author: Hessel Haagsma, Dieuwke Roelofs-Prins and Esther van Enckevort Edits: Update screenshots, data upload instructions w.r.t. move to EMX2 backend, add studies and services</p>

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Table A.1: (Continued)

Version: 4.0.1
Date: 23/07/2025
Author: Hessel Haagsma
Edits: Improved PDF rendering

Version: 4.1.0
Date: 01/09/2025
Author: Hessel Haagsma
Edits: Remove network inheritance, update data flow diagram

Version: 4.2.0
Date: 31/01/2026
Author: Petr Holub
Edits: Conversion from Google Doc to \LaTeX /Overleaf

Version: 4.3.0
Date: 01/02/2026
Author: Petr Holub
Edits: Data quality checks documentation and tooling updates

Version: 4.3.1
Date: 01/02/2026
Author: Petr Holub
Edits: Hyperlink fixes and data check documentation improvements

Version: 4.3.2
Date: 05/03/2026
Author: Petr Holub
Edits: Updated data quality checks, added information on k-anonymity for CollectionFacts

Version: 4.3.3
Date: 05/03/2026
Author: Petr Holub
Edits: Expanded CollectionFacts k-anonymity section with operational tooling scenarios and rationale for not enforcing l-diversity/t-closeness at Directory layer

B. Acknowledgments

This work is part of the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project, funded by the European Commission, topic H2020-INFRADEV-3-2015, Grant Agreement Nr 676550.